

ESTRUTURA CRISTALINA DO COMPOSTO CUATERNÁRIO SEMICONDUTOR
CuFeCrSe₃CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF THE QUATERNARY SEMICONDUCTOR COMPOUND
CuFeCrSe₃DELGADO, Gerzon E.^{1*}; DELGADO-NIÑO, Pilar², GRIMA-GALLARDO, Pedro^{3,4}¹ Laboratorio de Cristalografía, Departamento de Química, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida 5101, Venezuela² Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Libre, Av. Cr 70 53-40, Bogotá, Colombia³ Centro de Estudios de Semiconductores, Departamento de Física, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Los Andes, Mérida 5101, Venezuela⁴ Centro Nacional de Tecnologías Ópticas (CNTO) y Centro Investigaciones de Astronomía (CIDA), Mérida 5101, Venezuela

* Correspondence author
e-mail: gerzon@ula.ve

Received 14 April 2019; received in revised form 14 July 2019; accepted form 19 July 2019

RESUMO

Os compostos com estruturas ternárias da família da calcopirita Cu-III-Se₂ (III = Al, Ga, In, Cr) formam um amplo grupo de materiais semicondutores com diversas propriedades ópticas e elétricas, e a adição do composto binário FeSe produz ligas do tipo (Cu-III-Se₂)_{1-x}(Fe-Se)_x. Esses tipos de materiais têm recebido atenção crescente como promissores materiais termoelétricos devido à sua alta eficiência, propriedades de transporte sintonizáveis, alta abundância elementar e baixa toxicidade. Este trabalho buscou sintetizar e caracterizar estruturalmente um novo material pertencente a este sistema semicondutor com $x = \frac{1}{2}$, o composto quaternário CuFeCrSe₃. Este material foi preparado pela técnica de fusão e recozimento e sua estrutura foi refinada a partir do padrão de difração de raios-X usando o método de Rietveld. O padrão de raios X em pó foi composto principalmente de CuFeCrSe₃ (79,1%) com CuCr₂Se₄ (20,9%) aparecendo como fase secundária. A fase principal cristaliza com a simetria tetragonal no grupo espacial $P\bar{4}2c$ (Nº 112), $Z = 1$, com $a = 5.5082(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.943(1) \text{ \AA}$, $V = 332.01(1) \text{ \AA}^3$. O refinamento de 18 parâmetros instrumentais e estruturais levou a $R_p = 8,8\%$, $R_{wp} = 9,1\%$, $R_{exp} = 7,8\%$ e $S = 1,2$. Este material, pertencente ao sistema semicondutor I-II-III-VI₃, cristaliza com uma estrutura do tipo CuFeInSe₃ numa estrutura normal de adamantano. O CuFeCrSe₃ é um novo composto semicondutor relacionado à fase superiônica CuCrSe₂, e pode ser considerado como potencial candidato a aplicações termoelétricas de média temperatura.

Palavras-chave: Difração de raios X, estrutura cristalina, calcogenetos, semicondutores, síntese química.

ABSTRACT

The compounds with ternary structures of the chalcopyrite family Cu-III-Se₂ (III = Al, Ga, In, Cr) form a wide group of semiconductor materials with diverse optical and electrical properties, and the addition of FeSe binary compound produces alloys of the type (Cu-III-Se₂)_{1-x}(Fe-Se)_x. These types of materials have received increasing attention as promising thermoelectric materials due to their high efficiency, tunable transport properties, high elemental abundance and low toxicity. This work aims to synthesize and characterize structurally a new material belonging to this semiconductor system with $x = \frac{1}{2}$, the quaternary compound CuFeCrSe₃. This material was prepared by the melt and anneal technique and its structure was refined from X-ray powder diffraction pattern using the Rietveld method. The X-ray powder pattern was mainly composed of CuFeCrSe₃ (79.1%) with CuCr₂Se₄ (20.9%) appearing as secondary phase. The principal phase crystallizes with tetragonal symmetry in the space group $P\bar{4}2c$ (Nº 112), $Z = 1$, with $a = 5.5082(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.943(1) \text{ \AA}$, $V = 332.01(1) \text{ \AA}^3$. The refinement of 18 instrumental and structural parameters led to $R_p = 8.8 \%$, $R_{wp} = 9.1 \%$, $R_{exp} = 7.8 \%$ and $S = 1.2$. This material, belonging to the semiconductor system I-II-III-VI₃, crystallizes with a CuFeInSe₃-type structure in a normal adamantane-structure. CuFeCrSe₃ is a new semiconductor compound, related to the superionic phase CuCrSe₂, and can be considered as a potential candidate for medium-temperature thermoelectric applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The compounds with ternary structures of the chalcopyrite family Cu-III-Se₂ (III = Al, Ga, In, Cr) form a wide group of semiconductor materials with diverse optical and electrical properties (Shay and Wernik, 1974). They crystallize with tetragonal symmetry in the space group I $\bar{4}$ 2d (N°122), and the addition of a FeSe binary compound produces alloys of the type (I-III-Se₂)_{1-x}(Fe-Se)_x (Parthé, 1995). The synthesis and crystal structure characterization of some member with compositions Cu-Fe-III-S₃ ($x = \frac{1}{2}$), Cu-Fe₂-III-Se₄ ($x = \frac{2}{3}$) and Cu₂-Fe-III-Se₅ ($x = \frac{1}{3}$) have been reported (Delgado *et al.*, 2008; 2009; 2010; 2014; 2015; Grima-Gallardo *et al.*, 2000; 2001a; 2001b, 2007a, 2007b, 2015; Mora *et al.*, 2007; Flores-Cruz *et al.*, 2018). All these phases fulfill the rules of formation of adamantane compounds and belong to the normal semiconductor compound families (Parthé, 1995). These types of materials, Cu-based chalcogenides, have received increasing attention as promising thermoelectric materials due to their high efficiency, tunable transport properties, high elemental abundance and low toxicity (Wei *et al.*, 2019). In particular, the ternary CuCrSe₂ is considered a superionic crystal because exhibit ionic mobilities comparable to liquids while maintaining a periodic crystalline lattice (Niedziela *et al.*, 2018), and is a potential candidate for medium-temperature thermoelectric applications (Cheng *et al.*, 2015).

In this work, we report a detailed structural analysis of the quaternary semiconductor CuFeCrSe₃, a new member of the Cu-II-III-Se₃ family, which is a related compound of the superionic crystal CuCrSe₂.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Preparation

Starting materials (Cu, Fe, Cr, Se) with nominal purity of 99.99 % in the stoichiometric ratio were mixed together in an evacuated and sealed quartz tube with the inner walls previously carbonized in order to avoid reactions of the starting materials with the quartz ampoule. Polycrystalline ingots of about 1 g were prepared by the melt and anneal technique as previously

described (Grima-Gallardo *et al.*, 2000; Flores-Cruz *et al.*, 2018).

2.2. X-ray powder diffraction

A small quantity of the sample was ground mechanically in an agate mortar and pestle. The resulting fine powder was mounted on a flat zero-background holder covered with a thin layer of petroleum jelly. The X-ray powder diffraction data was collected at room temperature, in θ/θ reflection mode using a Siemens D5005 diffractometer equipped with an X-ray tube (CuK α radiation: $\lambda = 1.54059$ Å; 40kV, 30 mA) and a diffracted beam graphite monochromator. The specimen was scanned from 10-100° 2 θ , with a step size of 0.02° and counting time of 20 s. Quartz was used as an external standard. For the Rietveld refinement, the whole diffraction data was used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A search in the ICDD-PDF database (ICDD, 2013) using the software available with the diffractometer was performed, and one known +phases present in small quantities was readily identified: CuCr₂Se₄ (PDF N° 81-1986). The peak positions of each phase were extracted by means of single-peak profile-fittings carried out with the DIFFRACplus software. The remaining intense peaks corresponding to the phase of interest, CuFeCrSe₃, were readily indexed in a tetragonal cell with: $a = 5.51(2)$ Å and $c = 10.94(5)$ Å, using the program Dicvol04 (Boultif and Louër, 2004). A revision of the diffraction lines of the main phase taking into account the sample composition, unit cell parameters as well as the primitive cell suggested that this material is isostructural with the CuFeInSe₃-type compound, which crystallize in the tetragonal space group P $\bar{4}$ 2c (N° 112) (Mora *et al.*, 2007).

The Rietveld refinement (Rietveld, 1969) was carried out using the Fullprof program (Rodríguez-Carvajal, 1993). The atomic coordinates of CuFeInSe₃ (Mora *et al.*, 2007) were used as starting model for the quaternary CuFeCrSe₃. Atomic positions of the ternary CuCr₂Se₄ (Okonska-Kozłowska *et al.*, 1993) were included as secondary phase in the refinement. The angular dependence of the peak full width at half maximum (FWHM) was described by the Caglioti's formula (Caglioti *et al.*, 1958). Peak

shapes were described by the parameterized Thompson-Cox-Hastings pseudo-Voigt profile function (Thompson *et al.*, 1987). The background variation was described by a polynomial with six coefficients. The thermal motion of the atoms was described by one overall isotropic temperature factor. The results of the Rietveld refinement are summarized in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the observed, calculated and difference profile for the final cycle of Rietveld refinement. Atomic coordinates, isotropic temperature factor and bond distances are shown in Table 2. The final Rietveld refinement converged to the following weight fraction percentages: CuFeCrSe₃ (79.1%) and CuCr₂Se₄ (20.9%).

CuFeCrSe₃ is a normal adamantane-structure compound (Parthé, 1995). The Se atoms form a close-packed arrangement where each anion is coordinated by four cations located at the corners of a slightly distorted tetrahedron. All cations are similarly coordinated by four anions. Figure 2 shows a polyhedral view of the crystal structure with the four types of atoms-centered tetrahedra CuSe₄, FeSe₄, CrSe₄ and MSe₄ where all polyhedra are oriented in the same direction and are connected by the corners.

The interatomic distances are shorter than the sum of the respective ionic radii for structures tetrahedrally bonded (Shannon, 1976). The bond distances Cu-Se [2.42(4) Å], Fe-Se [2.43(4) Å] and Cr-Se [2.36(4) Å] are in good agreement with those observed in other chalcogenide compounds such as CuCrSe₂ (Hahn and de Lorent, 1957), CuInSe₂ (Knight, 1992), Fe₂CrSe₄, (Delgado and Sagredo, 2004), CuFe(Al,Ga,In)Se₃ (Mora *et al.*, 2007; Delgado *et al.*, 2009), CuFe₂(Al,Ga,In)Se₄ (Delgado *et al.*, 2008; Delgado *et al.*, 2015), CuNi(Ga,In)Se₃ (Delgado *et al.*, 2010), Cu₃NbSe₄ (Lu and Ibers, 1993) and Cu₃VSe₄ (Klepp and Gurtner, 2004).

CuFeCrSe₃ is a semiconductor compound with *n*-type conductivity (Grima-Gallardo *et al.*, 2000), related to the superionic phase CuCrSe₂, which can be used as thermoelectric material.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The new quaternary semiconductor compound CuFeCrSe₃ was synthesized by the melt and anneal technique and its crystal structure was characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis. Rietveld refinement from the X-ray powder data allowed to determine the crystal structure of this compound. The X-ray powder

pattern was mainly composed of CuFeCrSe₃ (79.1%) with CuCr₂Se₄ (20.9%) as secondary phase.

The new semiconductor compound CuFeCrSe₃, belonging to the semiconductor system Cu-II-III-Se₃, crystallizes in the tetragonal space group P4₂c, with a CuFeInSe₃-type structure. This is a new compound of the I-II-III-VI₃ family of semiconductors, with a normal adamantane-structure.

This quaternary material, related to the superionic phase CuCrSe₂, can be considered as a potential candidate for medium-temperature thermoelectric applications.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:

This work was supported by CDCHT-UCLA (Grant C-1885-14-05-B) and FONACIT (Grants LAB-97000821, PEII-1697 and 2011001341).

6. REFERENCES:

1. Shay J.L., Wernik J.H. *Ternary chalcopyrite semiconductors: Growth, electronic properties and applications*, Pergamon Press., Oxford, **1974**.
2. Parthé E. *Wurtzite and Sphalerite Structures*. In: J.H. Westbrook, R.L. Fleischer (eds), *Intermetallic Compounds, Principles and Applications*. Vol. 1, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK, **1995**.
3. Delgado, G.E., Mora, A.J., Grima-Gallardo, P., Quintero, M. *J. Alloys Comp.* **2008**, 454, 306.
4. Delgado, G.E., Mora, A.J., Contreras, J.E., Grima-Gallardo, P., Durán, S., Muñoz, M., Quintero, M. *Cryst. Res. Technol.* **2009**, 44, 548.
5. Delgado, G.E., Mora, A.J., Grima-Gallardo, P., Durán, S., Muñoz, M., Quintero, M. *Bull. Mater. Sci.* **2010**, 33, 637.
6. Delgado, G.E., Quintero, E., Tovar, R., Grima-Gallardo, P., Quintero, M. *J. Alloys Comp.* **2014**, 613, 143.
7. Delgado, G.E., Mora, A.J., Grima-Gallardo, P., Muñoz, M., Durán, S., Quintero, M., Briceño, J.M. *Bull. Mater. Sci.* **2015**, 38, 1061.
8. Grima-Gallardo, P., Molina, L., Quintero, M., Tovar, R., Ruiz, J., Quintero, E., Delgado, G.E., Maury, L. *phys. stat. sol.*

- (b), **2000**, 220, 377.
9. Grima-Gallardo, P., Cárdenas, K., Quintero, M., Ruiz, J., Delgado, G.E. *Mater. Res. Bull.* **2001**, 36, 861.
 10. Grima-Gallardo, P., Muñoz, M., Delgado, G.E., Briceño, J.M., Ruiz, J. *phys. stat. sol. (b)*, **2001**, 241, 1789.
 11. Grima-Gallardo, P., Muñoz, M., Durán, S., Delgado, G.E., Quintero, M., Ruiz, J. *Mater. Res. Bull.* **2007**, 42, 2067.
 12. Grima-Gallardo, P., Muñoz, M., Durán, S., Delgado, G.E., Quintero, M., Briceño, J.M., Ruiz, J. *phys. stat. sol. (a)*, **2007**, 204, 1093.
 13. Grima-Gallardo, P., Torres, S., Quintero, M., Nieves, L., Moreno, E., Delgado, G.E. *J. Alloys Comp.* **2015**, 630, 146.
 14. Mora, A.J., Delgado, G.E., Grima-Gallardo, P. *phys. stat. sol. (a)*, **2007**, 204, 547.
 15. Flores-Cruz, J.A., Delgado, G.E., Contreras, J., Quintero, M., Nieves, L., Grima-Gallardo, P. *Tchê Quím. J.* **2018**, 15, 224.
 16. Wei, T.R., Qin, Y., Deng, T., Song, Q., Jiang, B., Liu, R., Qiu, P., Shi, Z., Chen, L. *Sci. China Mater.* **2019**, 62, 8.
 17. Niedziela, J.L., Bansal, D., May, A.F., Ding, J., Lanigan-Atkins, T., Ehlers, G., Abernathy, D.L., Said, A., Delaire, O. *Nature Phys.* **2018**, 15, 73.
 18. Cheng, Y., Yang, J., Jiang, Q., Fu, L., Xiao, Y., Luo, Y., Zhang, D., Zhang, M. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **2015**, 98, 3975.
 19. International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD), *Powder Diffraction File (Set 1-65)*. Newtown Square, PA, USA, **2013**.
 20. Boultif, A., Louër, D. *J. App. Cryst.* **2004**, 37, 724.
 21. Rietveld, H.M. *J. App. Cryst.* **1969**, 2, 65.
 22. Rodriguez-Carvajal, J. *Phys. B: Cond. Matter*, **1993**, 192, 55.
 23. Okonska-Kozłowska, I., Kopyczok, J., Lutz, H.D., Stingl, T. *Acta Cryst. C.* **1993**, 49, 1448.
 24. Cagliotti, G., Paoletti, A., Ricci, F.P. *Nucl. Instrum.* **1958**, 3, 223.
 25. Thompson, P., Cox, D.E., Hastings, J.B. *J. App. Cryst.* **1987**, 20, 79.
 26. Shannon, S.D. *Acta Cryst. A.* **1976**, 32, 751.
 27. Hahn, H., de Lorent, V. *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **1957**, 290, 68.
 28. Knight, K.S. *Mater. Res. Bull.* **1992**, 27, 161.
 29. Delgado, G.E., Sagredo, V. *phys. stat. sol. (a)*, **2004**, 3, 421.
 30. Lu, Y.J., Ibers, J.A. *J. Solid State Chem.* **1993**, 107, 58.
 31. Klepp, K.O., Gurtner, D. *Z. Krystallogr. New Cryst. Struct.* **2004**, 215, 4.

Figure 1. Rietveld final plot of CuFeCrSe_3 . The lower trace is the difference curve between observed and calculated patterns. The Bragg reflections are indicated by vertical bars

Figure 2. Unit cell diagram for the compound CuFeCrSe_3 showing the tetrahedral around the cations

Table 1. Rietveld refinement results for CuFeCrSe_3

Molecular formula	CuFeCrSe_3	Molecular weight (g/mol)	1088.6
a (Å)	5.5082(2)	System	tetragonal
c (Å)	10.943(1)	Space group	$P\bar{4}2c$ (112)
V (Å ³)	332.01(3)	D_{calc} (g/cm ⁻³)	5.44
Z	1	Weight fraction (%)	79.1
R_p (%)	8.8	R_B (%)	8.5
R_{wp} (%)	9.1	R_{exp} (%) = 7.8	S = 1.2

$$R_p = 100 \frac{\sum |y_{\text{obs}} - y_{\text{calc}}|}{\sum |y_{\text{obs}}|} \quad R_B = 100 \frac{\sum_k |I_k - I_{c,k}|}{\sum_k I_k} \quad S = [R_{\text{wp}} / R_{\text{exp}}]$$

$$R_{\text{wp}} = 100 \left[\frac{\sum_w |y_{\text{obs}} - y_{\text{calc}}|^2}{\sum_w |y_{\text{obs}}|^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad R_{\text{exp}} = 100 \left[\frac{(N+C)}{\sum_w (y_{\text{obs}}^2)} \right]^{1/2} \quad N-P+C = \text{degrees of freedom}$$

Table 2. Atomic coordinates, isotropic temperature factors and bond distances (Å) for CuFeCrSe_3 , derived from the Rietveld refinement. $M = (\text{Cu}1+\text{Fe}1+\text{Cr}1)$

Atom	Ox.	Site	x	y	z	foc	B (Å ²)			
Cu	+1	2e	0	0	0	1	0.6(4)			
Fe	+2	2d	0	½	¼	1	0.6(4)			
Cr	+3	2b	½	0	¼	1	0.6(4)			
		2f	½	½	0	⅓	0.6(4)			
M		2f	½	½	0	⅓	0.6(4)			
		2f	½	½	0	⅓	0.6(4)			
Se	-2	8n	0.263(1)	0.251(1)	0.123(1)	1	0.6(4)			
Cu-Se		2.42(4)	Fe-Se		2.43(4)	Cr-Se		2.36(4)	M-Se	2.32(4)